

An investigation of the potential sources, transport mechanisms, and health impacts of particulate matter and toxic metals in the Saldanha Bay Municipality

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1. Introduction

This report is a summary of the work performed by Dr. Heleen Vos, Dr. Janine Colling, Ms. Isabella Braithwaite, Ms. Kereemang Gaoaaga, and Prof. Susanne Fietz at Stellenbosch University. This research was conducted in collaboration with Ms. René Toesie from the Municipality of Saldanha Bay and was supported by several citizens of the Municipality of Saldanha Bay who allowed the installation of samplers and sensors on their property. The work addresses the following aim: *To investigate the potential sources and transport mechanisms of particulate matter and potentially toxic metals¹ in the Saldanha Bay Municipality area to provide recommendations for possible mitigation strategies.*

1.1 What is air pollution and why is it relevant?

Air pollution is considered to be the biggest environmental threat to human health, being the fourth most deadly risk factor, following tobacco use, dietary risks, and high blood pressure [1]. Worldwide, air pollution causes 6.67 million premature deaths annually [1,2]. Considering the severe effects of air pollution, it is imperative to look at sources and impacts to propose preventative strategies for air pollution [2–8]. Among the multiple

¹ To improve readability, in this report the term "metal" will include metalloids such as arsenic (As) and antimony (Sb)

Figure 1. Examples of different types of air pollution: natural particulate matter emission from a shrubland area in the Northern Cape province (left), anthropogenic particulate matter emission from agricultural areas in the Free State province (middle), and anthropogenic emission associated with the transport of mining materials in the Western Cape province (right).

factors that can cause air pollution, fine, solid particles represent the largest threat to global human health [1]. These solid particles that are suspended in the air are commonly referred to as "dust" but in this report, the term particulate matter (PM) will be used throughout the study. Particulate matter can be subdivided by particle size, such as particles smaller than 10 micrometres in diameter (PM₁₀), particles smaller than 2.5 micrometres in diameter (PM_{2.5}), and particles smaller than 1 micrometre in diameter (PM₁). When inhaled, smaller particles such as PM_{2.5} can infiltrate further into the respiratory tracts and can therefore be more harmful than larger particles. Besides the size of the particle, the concentration and the harmful content of particulate matter need to be considered. For example, particulate matter can contain toxic metals or pathogens [9–13].

Particulate matter can be emitted by several natural and anthropogenic (originating from human activities) sources, see Figure 1 for examples from South Africa. Natural sources include ephemeral river and lake systems, dune systems, and volcanism. Often, natural particulate matter emission is associated with semi-arid and arid regions. Anthropogenic particulate matter is emitted through agricultural and mining activities, fires, vehicle exhausts, and combustion from industries, among others. Anthropogenic particles, especially the particles originating from

industrial activities, hold generally more toxic metals [14–20]. Over the last 100 years, the emission of anthropogenic particulate matter has increased due to the expansion and intensification of industrial activities and land use [21,22].

Besides a distinction on particle size and source type, air pollution can further be distinguished into ambient (outdoor) air pollution and household (indoor) air pollution. Household air pollution is mainly related to indoor activities such as the burning of solid fuels for cooking

or heating, whereas ambient air pollution originates outdoors, such as natural and industrial sources. The effects of household air pollution remain most significant in lower-income countries [1, 23–26], whereas globally, awareness of the harmful effects of household pollution and the availability of cooking alternatives lowered the air-quality associated mortality. However, the number of deaths from ambient air pollution stayed relatively stable and ambient air pollution caused more deaths than household pollution since 2008 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The number of deaths per 100,000 people globally from different types of air pollution over time. This graph shows a general decrease in deaths by household air pollution but a constant in the deaths by ambient particulate matter pollution¹. Data provided by HME, Global Burden of Disease Study (2019) and processed by Our World in Data [27].

¹ The death rates include both sexes and are age-standardized which means that it is calculated for one constant age distribution. This way, it is possible to account for an ageing population over time or allow comparisons between countries.

Key messages:

- Air pollution, especially suspended particles (particulate matter), is a global challenge threatening human health.
- Particulate matter can have natural and anthropogenic origins, such as industry, combustion, transportation, and mining.
- Fine particles, such as PM_{2.5}, are more commonly associated with anthropogenic activities and arguably more harmful for human health because it can penetrate deeper into the respiratory system. These fine particles generally also have higher toxic metal content.

1.2 Air pollution in South Africa

In South Africa, approximately 73 per 100,000 people die annually from air pollution. Ambient particulate matter pollution is particularly of concern causing 81% of the air pollution-related deaths (Figure 3). Similar to the global trend (Figure 2), the number of deaths related to household air pollution has declined over the past 20 years, whereas the impact of ambient air pollution remained consistent. The effects of ambient air pollution are especially significant for infants in their first years and elderly people [28–33] (Figure 4). Most air pollution in South Africa has been associated with traffic, mining, the

energy sector [34–38], agriculture [39–41], and natural dust [42, 43]. Despite the wide variety and relevance of air pollution, there are currently only 21 governmental monitoring stations in South Africa which routinely measure the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration [44]. Only one of these $PM_{2.5}$ monitoring stations is installed in the Western Cape Province, despite the large transport and mining industry in this province. Considering the high variability of particulate matter sources and exposure risk to particulate matter, it is necessary to have a precise understanding of the sources and composition of the particles that people are exposed to.

Death rate from different types of air pollution in South Africa

Figure 3. The number of deaths per 100,000 people in South Africa per major air pollution type over time¹. Data provided by HME, Global Burden of Disease Study (2019) and processed by Our World in Data [27].

¹ The death rates include both sexes and are age-standardized which means that it is calculated for one constant age distribution. This way it is possible to account for an ageing population over time or allow comparisons between countries.

Deaths in South Africa by ambient particulate matter pollution

Figure 4. The number of total deaths in South Africa from ambient particulate matter pollution in 2019 per age group, showing the high impact that ambient air pollution has on both older and younger people. Data provided by HME, Global Burden of Disease Study (2019) and processed by Our World in Data [45].

Key messages:

- In South Africa, roughly 73 out of 100,000 deaths are associated with air pollution. 82% of these deaths can be linked with ambient (outdoor) particulate matter.
- The number of deaths due to ambient particulate matter has remained relatively stable since 1990.
- Accurate assessment of the risks and consequences of air pollution in South Africa are hindered by limited monitoring practices and spatial coverage.

1.3 Particulate matter emission from Saldanha Bay

Air pollution is a concern in the vicinity of Saldanha Bay, an area located in the Western Cape Province and on the west coast of South Africa (Figure 5). Saldanha Bay's port is an industrial hub responsible for the processing and exporting of large quantities of mining materials, especially iron ore and magnesium ores mined in the Northern Cape Province. In addition to ore processing, the industrial area surrounding the port, the Besaansklip industrial area, produces metals such as lead, copper, and zinc, and steel, including galvanized steel, for export. Industrial activities in the area have consistently expanded since the early 2000s [46]. Future development plans for the industrial area include increasing the iron ore storage and handling capacity, expanding the rail and port facilities, establishing biofuel and

gas production facilities, and generally expanding industrial operations and industrial capacity [47, 48].

The transportation, storage, and processing of mining materials in this region have led to the visible emission of particulate matter (Figure 6). Additionally, the transportation of mining materials via rail and road has been identified as a potential source of particulate matter [47, 49]. Since this area also features densely populated residential zones and key national protected areas that are exposed to potential industrial and other anthropogenic pollution, the particulate matter emission led to concerns about the impact of particulate matter on the public health in the residential areas surrounding the port. In total 123,000 people, including those residing in informal settlements live in the Saldanha Bay Municipality [50] and could be exposed to industrial and other anthropogenic pollution.

Figure 5. A map of the Saldanha Bay Municipality including the major towns in this area, the industrial area and the port area, the West Coast National Park, the major roads, and the railroad. The locations of the climate station on Langebaanweg, the two monitoring methods, the PurpleAir PM_{2.5} sensor and the BSNE particulate matter are shown. These methods are further described in Sections 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5.

Figure 6. Photos of the Saldanha Bay industrial area illustrating the red particulate matter deposited in this area at the entrance to the iron ore port (left), and on rail waggons (right).

1.4 Research on particulate matter from 2015 to 2022

To support health risk assessments in the residential areas surrounding the port, the Saldanha Bay Municipality installed particulate matter monitoring equipment in 2015. This equipment consists of a monitoring station that measured the hourly PM_{2.5} concentration in the town of Saldanha from 2015 to 2018, and several particulate matter traps that allow an assessment of the particulate matter deposition from 2015 to 2022. The data is publicly available at <https://sbm.gov.za/environmental/>. This data has been analysed in an article (Vos et al., sub.) that has been submitted for review to a scientific international peer-review journal. The study furthermore investigates the regions that might be impacted by this particulate matter. The results from this study were used to design the sampling strategy used in this report. Below we summarise the highlights of the submitted article.

1.4.1 Trends in particulate matter concentrations and drivers

The average PM_{2.5} concentration measured in Saldanha was 7.1 µg m⁻³. Weather patterns, especially wind direction and wind speed, were the most important factors influencing the PM_{2.5} concentration. The PM_{2.5} concentration at Saldanha was lower when the wind blew from the southwest, from the ocean than when the wind came from the east, from inland. Since the main wind direction is from the south to southwest, the town of Saldanha likely received less particulate matter from the industrial area than areas north of this region. The wind patterns also caused some seasonal variability since south and southwestern winds from the Atlantic Ocean are more common in summer, leading to an overall lower summer particulate matter concentration. Despite the continuous development of the industrial area over the study period from 2015 to 2018, a corresponding increase in PM_{2.5} concentration was not observed at the monitoring station in Saldanha. The particulate matter deposition monitoring also did not show significant increases from 2015 to 2022. These deposition measurements did display a very high spatial variability within a small area illustrating the complexity of extensive particulate matter monitoring to be considered in health risks assessments.

1.4.2 Transport pathways of particulate matter

To understand which regions are mainly impacted by the suspended particles that were monitored in the Saldanha Bay municipality, the trajectories of the dust particles were calculated. For this, the Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) Model was used. This model calculates the transport route of particles emitted from a certain point at a certain time allowing us to project which areas could be

impacted by the emissions in Saldanha. We determined the trajectories over 24 hours and over 120 hours (Figure 7). Most particles travelled northward over the first 24 hours, which matches with the general southerly winds. However, after 120 hours a split in the trajectory can be observed: most particles move either north along the African west coast, or southeast, towards the southeast of South Africa and the Indian Ocean. These graphs (Figure 7) show the reach of particle emissions and the possible relevance beyond the regional scale.

Figure 7. The percentage of the particles per km² emitted daily from the industrial hub of Saldanha Bay from 2015 to 2022. Trajectories were calculated using the HYSPLIT trajectory modelling. The figures show the spatial distribution of the trajectories after 24 hours (left) and 120 hours (right) of suspension. Note the difference in axis between the two graphs, caused by the spreading, and therefore dilution, of the particles.

Key messages:

- The Saldanha Bay Municipality is an important industrial hub, which is responsible for the transport and processing of mining materials and the production of different metals and steel, among others.
- The industrial activities led to the visible emission of particulate matter implying concerns for public health and the environment. However, no relationship between industrial expansion and particulate matter concentration was observed from 2015 to 2022.
- The particulate matter monitoring indicates wind direction as major decisive factor for particulate matter concentration, explaining seasonal changes.

2. Aims and objectives of the extended study presented here

The study from Vos et al. (sub), described above, showed a high spatial variability of the particulate matter in the Saldanha Bay municipality and highlighted a poor understanding of the possible health effects of this dust. To address these knowledge gaps, the project presented in this report aims to quantify the particulate matter and address the associated risks for public health in the greater Saldanha Bay. To do so, the particulate matter and its chemical content were analysed and used to assess the possible health risks. In combination with weather data, the results can furthermore provide insights into the sources of the particulate matter, the main transport mechanisms, and the areas that are at a higher risk. This project addressed the following four objectives:

1. Quantify the suspended PM_{2.5} in the residential areas of the Saldanha Bay municipality.
2. Assess the possible health risks of the particulate matter.
3. Determine the possible sources of the particulate matter.
4. Develop suggestions for future research.

3. Methods

3.1 Approaches for measurements and discrete sampling

Two main approaches were used: continuous PM_{2.5} concentration measurements using a sensor (Approach 1, details given in section 3.2), and low-resolution sampling using particulate matter samplers (Approach 2, details given in section 3.3). The determination of the health risks and the origin of particulate matter differ between the two approaches whereby the difference can be summarised as amount and

composition. Simplified, a health risk can be high due to excessive amounts of low-risk compounds, or due to low amounts of highly toxic compounds. Where the PM_{2.5} measurements address the quantity of suspended particles (approach 1), the sampling of particulate matter (approach 2) gives insight into the presence of toxic compounds. Using both approaches, we assessed both the quantity and the composition to assess the public health risks.

3.2 Choice of locations for the monitoring and sampling

The monitoring equipment was placed in residential areas to assess residents' health risks. For example, the particulate matter traps were placed across the main towns of the Municipality allowing to assess small scale spatial variability: Vredenburg, Saldanha, Bay, Langebaan and St. Helena Bay, and in the Blouwater Bay neighbourhood (Figure 5). The placement of the monitoring sensors was chosen by considering local wind patterns. The predominant wind direction around Saldanha Bay is from the south towards the north, with occasional north-to-south winds, which are more common during winter. Consequently, residential areas north of the local industrial zone and port, such as the town of Vredenburg, would presumably be most affected by particulate matter of local anthropogenic origin. For this reason, the PurpleAir sensor which measures the PM_{2.5} concentration was placed in Vredenburg (Figure 8). The monitoring and sampling equipment was mounted on the private properties of volunteering citizens to prevent theft and/or vandalism.

3.3 Approach 1

3.3.1 PurpleAir PM_{2.5} monitoring equipment

The Purple Air sensor is a PM_{2.5} sensor that has widely been used in studies on

air quality [51–54]. The PurpleAir sensor was installed before August 2023 in Vredenburg (Figure 5). As outlined above (Section 1.4.1) this area was chosen because it is the largest town in the municipality and is likely to capture the major air masses from the industrial area. The PurpleAir sensor allows measurements of the concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ every two minutes but gives no insight into the content of the particulate matter or the total quantity of particles in the air since particles larger than 2.5 micrometres are excluded from the measurements. The data from the PurpleAir was converted into hourly average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration to visualise temporal patterns, and daily average to allow comparison to national and international health standards (see section 3.2.2). The data was furthermore corrected for the humidity data, the formula of which is described in Appendix 1.

3.3.2 Determination of human health risks based on $PM_{2.5}$ concentration

The concentration of particulate matter is generally seen as one of the most important identifiers of air pollution and predictors of health risks [14–20, 55, 56]. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has set a guideline suggesting that exposure should be limited to a maximum average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration of $15 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ daily and $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ annually [57] (Table 1). Recognizing the need for air quality standards, South Africa has implemented the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS), which determines the maximum allowable levels for both daily and annual average concentrations of $PM_{2.5}$ [58]. These standards have been adapted for 2030 to increase air quality conditions (Table 1). It should be noted that both the daily WHO standard and the daily NAAQS standard have a frequency of exceedance of four, meaning that the daily standard can be crossed four days per year (ca. 1.1%) to still be considered within the guidelines. The $PM_{2.5}$ concentration measured by a PurpleAir sensor in Vredenburg was compared to these national- and international health standards to assess the general air quality in this town.

Figure 8. The PurpleAir sensor (left) and mounting of the PurpleAir in Vredenburg (right).

Table 1. The maximum allowable $PM_{2.5}$ concentration prescribed by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS) and the World Health Organisation (WHO). *The daily average has a frequency of exceedance of four, meaning that the daily value can be crossed four times per year to still be considered within the guidelines.

	Current NAAQS standard	NAAQS standard in 2030	WHO standard
Daily average*	$40 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	$20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	$15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
Annual average	$20 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	$15 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$	$5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$

3.3.3 Determination of $PM_{2.5}$ origin

To determine the possible origin of the particulate matter, an hourly average of the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration was calculated. This data was then combined with the wind data from a climate station in Langebaanweg to allow visualisation of the relationship between wind patterns and $PM_{2.5}$ concentration using polar plots [59, 60]. These plots show the average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration that can be associated with specific wind directions and wind velocities over the monitoring period, from which the general direction of the sources of particulate matter can be derived.

3.4 Approach 2

3.4.1 BSNE Particulate matter sampler

The sampler used in this study is the BSNE (Big Spring Number Eight), a widely used trap that collects ambient particles (Figure 9). This low-cost instrument has advantages in a South African context as it requires very little maintenance and no electricity. However, this instrument has a much higher efficiency for particles of a larger grain size, which means finer particles ($PM_{2.5}$) are less represented by the captured particulate matter [61]. The

BSNE samplers used for this study were coated with a Teflon layer, to prevent contamination of the particulate matter from the metal sampler. In total, five samplers were deployed in August 2023, see Figure 5 and Figure 10, and samples were collected approximately every 2 months to ensure the amount of each sample was large enough for further analyses. Due to the optimization of the sampling technique, the particulate matter samples that were sampled from 18 September to 13 November 2023 were used for further analyses in this report.

After sampling, the mass of the particulate matter (mg) was converted to a horizontal particulate matter flux ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$) using the surface area of the entrance of the particulate matter sampler (10 cm^2), and the number of monitoring days (56 days, see also Appendix 2 for the calculation of the horizontal particulate matter flux). Subsequently, the elemental composition of the particulate matter was analysed using an Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometer (ICP-MS). The concentration of 21 elements was measured by the ICP-MS and represented in part per million (ppm, also mg/kg). The elements that were analysed and their abbreviations are summarised in Chapter 8.1).

Figure 9. Schematic overview of the BSNE sampler, showing the movement of the particulate matter with orange arrows and the movement of wind in blue. The particles that fall through the mesh and accumulate in the bottom of the sampler, and the air that travels through the top.

St. Helena Bay

Langebaan

Vredenburg

Blouwater Bay

Saldanha

Figure 10. The location of the five particulate matter samplers installed in the Saldanha Bay Municipality area.

3.4.2 Hazard index of potentially toxic metals

Many studies have described the harmful effects of metals that are commonly emitted by industrial activities [e.g., 14, 18, 47–50]. For this study, we focussed on the presence of eight metals and their potential toxic effects: As, Pb, Cd, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, and Cu. For simplicity, the remainder of the report will refer to these elements as the 'toxic metals'. These metals were selected due to their possible risks of poisoning and their association with mining and smelting activities [65–67]. Zn was excluded from the analyses due to possible contamination of this particulate matter from the sampler. To determine the impact of toxic metals in particulate matter, a model from the United States Environmental Protection Agency [68] was used. This model calculates the chemical daily intake (CDI) of toxic metals via inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. The calculation of this intake is based on the concentration of these elements within the particulate matter together with certain assumptions made on the lung capacity, body weight, skin surface, and exposure time, among others. Details on this model and the calculations can be found in Appendix 3. Combining the three types of intakes (inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact) with the bioaccumulation factor and the reference dose gives the total hazard indication. When this value is above 1, there are significant health risks, whereby a higher hazard index indicates

an increased health risk. A hazard index below 1 indicates a non-significant health risk.

3.4.3 Determination of particulate matter origin

The concentrations of the 21 measured elements were further used for a comparison with the elemental composition of the upper crust by calculating the enrichment factor (EF). Details on this calculation can be found in Appendix 4. Hereby, an enrichment factor of more than 10 would indicate an anthropogenic component of the dust, meaning that there are likely particles of an anthropogenic origin.

3.5 Weather conditions

To understand the transport of particulate matter, and therefore the source of these particles, the wind conditions were taken into account. Climate data were collected at a weather station in Langebaanweg (see Figure 5 and Appendix 5 for more information on this climate data). The general wind direction in this region is from the south to southwest, with some occasional strong northern winds (Figure 11). The wind conditions during the PurpleAir measurements (from August to December) and the particulate matter sampling (September 18 to November 13) were relatively similar to that of the annual average (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Windrose plots illustrate the wind conditions during 2023 (left), during the period of $PM_{2.5}$ monitoring (middle) and during the period of discrete particulate matter sampling (right). The segments at different angles represent the wind directions, the colours represent different wind speed ranges, and the length of the lines in each segment indicates the frequency of wind from that direction at that speed. Hereby, a northern wind represents wind that travels from the north to the south.

3.6 Key messages

4. Results

4.1 Approach 1: $PM_{2.5}$ concentration monitoring in Vredenburg

4.1.1 $PM_{2.5}$ concentration patterns

The hourly and daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in Vredenburg calculated from PurpleAir data is shown in Figure 12. The total average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in Vredenburg was $5.4 \mu g m^{-3}$ but shows hourly values as high as $85 \mu g m^{-3}$. These higher concentrations are likely event-based, meaning they are driven by specific weather conditions, natural conditions, or anthropogenic activities. The $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in Saldanha measured by the Saldanha Bay Municipality from 2015 to 2018 showed an average concentration of $7.1 \mu g m^{-3}$ even though Vredenburg would experience more wind travelling from the industrial area. Since these measurements were done during different years, it is difficult to say with certainty whether Saldanha receives a higher particulate matter concentration than Vredenburg.

4.1.2 Health risks associated with $PM_{2.5}$ concentration

The daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration crosses the WHO standard on seven days (4.6%), the current NAAQS on two days (1.3%), and the NAAQS in 2030 on three days (2.0%) (Figure 12). This indicates that the daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration does not conform to the international guidelines and the national NAAQS guidelines of 2030, assuming a similar pattern of $PM_{2.5}$ concentration throughout the rest of the year. The measured annual average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration of $5.4 \mu g m^{-3}$ remains within the health recommendations for the annual concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ of the NAAQS and is slightly above that of the WHO. However, monitoring over a full year is necessary to compare the measured concentrations with the health standards with certainty. Despite the crossing of daily values, the average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration measured at Vredenburg can still be regarded as low in comparison to other regions in South Africa, as shown by the measurements summarised by Altieri et al. [44]. This $PM_{2.5}$ concentration also lies below the concentration of which large-

Figure 12. The average hourly and daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration as measured by the PurpleAir at Vredenburg. The dotted lines represent the maximum daily concentration according to the South African guidelines currently (black) and in 2030 (grey) and the WHO air quality guideline (green).

scale and global studies have determined the associated mortality rate [69–72]. The health risks of the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration can therefore be considered small, but knowledge of the population and dust content is necessary to make statements on the health effects with certainty.

4.1.3 Evaluation of the $PM_{2.5}$ origin for the Vredenburg and Saldanha area

The Polar plot from Vredenburg from August to September (Figure 13) shows the relationship between the wind direction, wind speed, and the measured $PM_{2.5}$. The relationship between these values is generally similar to those observed for the Saldanha Bay monitoring period from 2015 to 2018, namely that strong northeastern winds are most strongly associated with high $PM_{2.5}$ concentration (Figure 13). Eastern winds are, however, relatively uncommon wind conditions

for this area (Figure 8), meaning that the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration of these winds might be high, but that the total quantity of $PM_{2.5}$ provided by this dust source might be less relevant. It cannot be stated with certainty what causes the high particulate matter concentration in Vredenburg, and to which extent this is caused by natural or anthropogenic processes. The wind originating from the direction of the iron ore terminal to the southeast of Vredenburg shows a slightly elevated $PM_{2.5}$ concentration. Lastly, a high concentration of dust is observed at low wind speeds (below 2 m/s) regardless of the direction. More particulate matter sensors measuring the air conditions simultaneously could give better insight into the general pollution in this area. This is a topic that is being addressed in current research that relies on the installation of multiple locally manufactured, low-cost sensors.

Figure 13. The polar plot measured at the Vredenburg station (top left) and the Saldanha Bay station (bottom left) and the location of these measurements and the location of the port and industrial area, the train tracks, smelters, and quarries (right).

Key messages:

- The average $PM_{2.5}$ concentration at Vredenburg is $5.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. The daily concentration crossed the national standard on two days, and the international WHO standard for seven days during the period from August to December 2023.
- The health risks associated with the $PM_{2.5}$ concentration in Vredenburg are likely small when only considering the quantity of the particles.
- The peak $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations events measured during that time appear to be brought by a strong northeastern wind. This suggests that sources of particulate matter northeast of Vredenburg should also be investigated.

4.2 Approach 2: Metal content in collected total particulate matter sampling

4.2.1 The chemical content of the particulate matter

Figure 14 shows the metal composition and the enrichment factor of the particles collected at the five sampling stations. The compositions of the different stations follow a similar pattern, whereby Al and Fe are the elements with the highest concentrations in the particulate matter. As discussed in section 3.5.2, the potentially

toxic metals considered here are As, Co, Cu, Cd, Cr, Ni, Mn, and Pb. Figure 15 shows the total flux of particulate matter, the concentration of potentially toxic metals, and the flux of the potentially toxic metals (see Appendix 2 for flux determination). The total particulate matter flux is the highest in Blouwater Bay and the lowest in St. Helena Bay (Figure 15), which can be explained by the distance from the industrial area (see Figure 5 for a map of the station locations). Despite the high toxic metal content in the dust in Vredenburg, the total toxic metal flux in this area is lower than that in Blouwater Bay, due to the high quantity of dust here.

Figure 14. The concentration of selected elements in the particulate matter samples (top), and enrichment factors of these elements compared to the upper crust composition and normalized to Al (bottom).

Figure 15. The total particulate matter flux (left), the concentration of toxic metals in the dust (middle), and the flux of these toxic metals (right) per monitoring site.

4.2.2 Evaluation of the hazard index of toxic metals present in the particulate matter

There is a strong enrichment of toxic metals in the dust measured in the Saldanha Bay municipality (Figure 14). To assess the risks of these metals, a hazard

index for children and adults proposed by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) has been calculated, for an illustration of the outcome see Figure 16; for details on the calculation see Appendix 3. A hazard index above 1 indicates there is a probability that non-carcinogenic effects

may occur and this probability is likely to increase as the hazard index increases [65]. The calculated hazard indices differ per sample site and element, indicating the variability of the particulate matter content in this area. The hazard index calculated for both children and adults remains below 1, which indicates that the

probability of negative effects is likely not significant. It should be noted that the hazard index for children is close to the threshold for Cr, Co, and Pb. This indicates the possible threat that these elements pose with an increase in emission of these elements.

Figure 16. The hazard index for adults (top) and children (bottom) calculated per element at each sampling site. Index calculations followed guidelines established by the US EPA [68] and are described in more detail in Appendix 3.

4.2.3 Origin indicator of elemental content and flux

To determine the enrichment of elements, the elemental concentration is compared to that of the upper crust (see Figure 14 and Appendix 2 for the calculations). Many metals show enrichment factors over a value of 10, which indicates anthropogenic enrichment of these elements. For example, the concentration of Pb (Figure 14) is on average 64 times higher than the global average concentration of the upper crust, which suggests the input of an anthropogenic source. The dust flux (Figure 15) is the highest in Blouwater Bay, followed by Langebaan, Vredenburg, and

Saldanha, and the lowest in St. Helena Bay. This is comparable to the finding described by Vos et al. (sub) and suggests the industrial area is a likely source of the particulate matter. When considering the toxic metal flux, In Blouwater Bay and Langebaan, two places in close proximity to the industrial area, the concentration of Pb is relatively high. The high toxic metal fluxes encountered at Vredenburg are especially caused by Mn. This high flux of Mn could be caused by the train tracks close to the town, where Mn is being transported. These analyses show the importance of considering the heterogeneity of particulate matter within the study area.

Key messages:

- Highest particulate matter fluxes are measured in Blouwater Bay. The concentration of toxic metals is the highest in Vredenburg
- The hazard indices indicate that there is a insignificant risk of the toxic metals in the dust. However, children are at a much higher health risk than adults and the values of Cr, Pb, and Co are close the threshold values.
- The particulate matter is enriched in metals of anthropogenic origin.

5. Summary

5.1.1 Health risks linked to toxic metals of particulate matter

The annual $PM_{2.5}$ concentration monitored in Vredenburg remained below the current and 2030 national standards (NAAQS), and the WHO standard, whereas the daily concentration crosses both standards but stays relatively close to the allowed frequency of exceedance. The $PM_{2.5}$ concentration previously monitored in Saldanha from 2015 to 2018 has shown similar low risks based on the concentration of ambient fine particles alone. Considering the proximity of the monitoring station to the industrial area and the major wind direction, it is reasonable to assume that the other urban areas in the study region experience similar or lower $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations. The content of the particulate matter shows that the heavy metals do not pose any significant risk since the hazard indices calculated remain below the threshold value. However, it should be noted that increases in toxic metal emissions should be taken seriously. This is especially the case considering the risk for children, and especially for the elements Cr, Co and Pb. For both the $PM_{2.5}$ content of toxic metals, the health risks during the monitoring period can be regarded as low, but any increase should be prevented.

5.1.2 Origin of particulate matter in Saldanha and Vredenburg

The particulate matter content captured in 2023 across the greater Saldanha Bay area showed a strong enrichment with potentially toxic metals of anthropogenic origin at all five sampling stations. The particulate matter captured in Saldanha from 2015 to 2018 likely originated from the northeast to the southwest, pointing to the general industrial area (Vos et al., sub). The peak $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations measured at Vredenburg originate mainly from the northeast. It cannot be excluded that

industrial particulate matter can reach this town, but the peak concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ is likely not caused by the industrial area. However, the enrichment in elements that have been associated with mining and smelting activities, such as Mn, Pb, and Cr, show an influence from the industrial area.

The difference in the origin of particulate matter in the different towns where the particulate matter was analysed is reflected in a difference in the chemistry. The particulate matter in Vredenburg has a higher concentration of toxic metals, especially in Mn. This high concentration of Mn can be caused by the proximity of the manganese train tracks that cross close to the town. The towns closest to the industrial area are especially enriched in Pb whereas in towns further away from the port such as Saldanha Bay and St. Helena Bay, the Cr content is especially high. These differences in concentration could be caused by different proximities to industries, and certain particles and metals being deposited more quickly than others during the transport of particulate matter. More research on the origin and transport of these metals is necessary to understand these processes better.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study describes the particulate matter concentration and content across the Saldanha Bay municipality. The analyses in this report show that the particulate matter in this region does not generally pose a high risk to public health. However, the toxic metal content in this area should be taken seriously and not increased, especially to protect the impact on children's health. The higher risks that particulate matter from this area poses to children should be addressed considering 25% of the people living in this municipality are underage [73]. To comply with the national air quality guidelines of 2030, the daily $PM_{2.5}$ concentration

should decrease. To ensure this, the exact sources of these particles need to be understood better.

Due to uncertainty in the precise sources of particulate matter, it is difficult to determine one specific method of particulate matter mitigation. For future action, it would be recommended to monitor the emission and particulate matter content from specific industries. Understanding the specific sources and their characteristics will help pinpoint the high-risk emissions and develop appropriate mitigation measures. Hereby the focus should not only be on the visible, highly emissive sources, such as the iron ore port, but also the sources that have a lower emission but emit possibly more harmful particles, such as smelting activities.

7. Future work

7.1 Health data

To make a more precise assessment of the health effects of particulate matter, the health statistics within the municipality should be studied. This data would give insight into the number of lung- and cardiovascular diseases, possible signs of heavy metal intoxication, and causes of deaths. This knowledge would help understand the spatial pattern of reported public health problems.

7.2 Pathogen and allergen analyses

An important factor in the health risks of particulate matter is the presence of microbial organisms that could harm public health such as pathogens and allergens. At the moment, sampling on the microbial organisms has been performed and will be analysed by the University of Pretoria.

7.3 Extent sampling period and monitoring efforts

This report presents five months of PM_{2.5} monitoring and two months of monitoring the chemical content of particulate matter. To improve the understanding of the patterns of particulate matter, this period should be extended. The six months of monitoring might not capture the general, long-term particulate matter conditions, or any significant industrial activities outside the monitoring period. It is recommended to continue the monitoring efforts, especially when the industrial areas continue to expand. So far, the monitoring has only been performed at one town, and can therefore not exactly represent towns such as Saldanha, Langebaan, or St. Helena Bay. So far, monitoring of the air quality has been performed in urban areas, which allows an assessment of the air and particulate matter to which the general public is exposed to.

7.4 The concentration of elements in the air and characteristics of size classes

The chemical content of the particulate matter and the concentration of the fine PM_{2.5} particles have been measured. This data can give a general indication of the health risks, but the precise concentration of toxic elements in the air and the concentration of PM_{2.5} has not been measured. Measuring the exact quantity of toxic metals (in µg m⁻³) that people are exposed to can be done by sampling particulate matter on filters. This would allow a more precise assessment of the air quality. Also, the data presented in this report has a knowledge gap when it comes to the particle size classes. The PurpleAir data represents the concentration of the particulate matter below PM_{2.5} and gives no insight into the PM₁, PM₁₀, or the concentration of the total particulate matter. In contrast, the particles sampled by the BSNE sampler,

are mainly particles larger than PM_{2.5} and the chemical content will therefore mainly represent the larger particles. This data gap can be solved by analysing the different size classes separately. This can be done using a Quantitative Evaluation of Minerals by Scanning Electron Microscopy (QEM-SCAN) which gives information on the mineralogy, chemical

content, and particle size of individual particles. Another method that could contribute to the knowledge gap is the use of active particulate matter samplers that capture a wide range of particulate matter. This would offer an extensive analysis of the particle size distribution and the relationship between the particle size and chemical content.

8. Terminology overview

Abbreviation	Meaning
Particulate Matter (PM)	The particles, either solid or liquid, that are suspended in the air. Particulate matter is often referred to as dust and can originate from both natural and anthropogenic processes. These particles are generally quite small and can be subdivided by size: PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , and PM ₁₀ see below.
Anthropogenic	Anything that originates from a human activity. In the case of particulate matter, common sources are traffic, combustion, and industrial processes.
BSNE	Abbreviation for Big Spring Number Eight. A common particulate matter sampler that captures particles using the natural movement of the wind.
Hazard index	A term introduced by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) to describe the risk of a certain element for public health. An extensive description of this term and associated calculations is in Appendix 3.
HYSPLIT	Abbreviation from the Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory Model. A model that calculates, among others, the trajectory of particles emitted from a certain point at a certain time.
PM ₁	Particulate matter with a size below 1 micrometre (µm) or 0.001 millimetres (mm)
PM _{2.5}	Particulate matter with a size below 2.5 micrometres (µm) or 0.0025 millimetres (mm)
PM ₁₀	Particulate matter with a size below 10 micrometres (µm) or 0.01 millimetres (mm)
Polar plot	A type of graph that shows the relationship between the wind velocity, wind direction, and contaminate concentration (in this case, the PM _{2.5} concentration).
Purple Air	A small sensor that measures the PM _{2.5} concentration at a 2-minute interval. More information can be found in references [52,54] or https://www2.purpleair.com/
NAAQS	The National Ambient Air Quality Standards developed by the South African government to prescribe, among others, the maximum allowed PM _{2.5} concentration
WHO	The World Health Organisation
Toxic metals	In this report, the term toxic metals will be used to describe the elements Cr, Cd, Co, Cu, Pb, Mn, and Ni. More elements have been described to be toxic at certain levels, but these elements are generally the most important concerning mining and smelting activities.
EF	Enrichment factor of particulate matter. This is calculated by comparing the chemical composition of the particulate matter with that of the upper continental crusts. More information on this value can be found in the appendix.

8.1 Elemental abbreviation

Abbreviation	Full name
Al	Aluminium
Si	Silicon
V	Vanadium
Cr	Chromium
Mn	Manganese
Fe	Iron
Co	Cobalt
Ni	Nickel
Cu	Copper
Zn	Zinc
As	Arsenic
Se	Selenium
Sr	Strontium
Mo	Molybdenum
Cd	Cadmium
Sn	Tin
Sb	Antimony
Ba	Barium
Hg	Mercury
Pb	Lead

9. Stakeholders

This project was done in collaboration with the following stakeholder at the Saldanha Bay Municipality:

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Appendix

1. PurpleAir correction

The PM_{2.5} concentration measured by the PurpleAir is influenced by the humidity value. To correct for this influence the following formula from Barkjohn et al. [52] was used:

$$PM_{2.5} = 0.524 * PA_{cf_1} - 0.0862 * RH + 5.75$$

Hereby, RH is the relative humidity measured by the PurpleAir, and PA_{cf_1} is the average PM_{2.5} concentration (in µg m⁻³) measured by the PurpleAir.

2. BSNE flux calculations

To analyse the chemical makeup of the dust, we set up 5 Big Spring Number Eights (BSNE) particulate matter samplers, which are passive dust samplers designed to capture horizontally traveling particles. These samplers were chosen for their affordability, low maintenance requirements, and lack of electricity needs, allowing us to measure simultaneously at various locations. However, it is worth noting that these samplers are more effective at capturing larger particles like silt and sand [61,74–76]. As a result, our measurements might overemphasize natural mineral particles and underestimate clay or combustion particles.

We collected dust samples from September 8 to November 13 using the BSNE samplers. To ensure comprehensive dust sampling, we used Milli-Q water to extract dust from the BSNE samplers. Subsequently, we freeze-dried and weighed the samples to determine the total dust mass. To convert the dust mass and individual elements into horizontal flux q (in mg m⁻² day⁻¹), we considered the BSNE's opening size of 10 cm² and the 66 days of sampling.

3. Hazard index

For this study, we will focus on the presence of seven heavy metals and the possible toxic effects of these metals: Pb, Cd, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, and Zn. These metals are chosen by their possible risks of toxicity and their association with mining and smelting activities [65, 66, 67]. To determine the impact of toxic metals in particulate matter, the chemical daily intake of toxic metals (CDI) via inhalation through the mouth and nose (D_{inh}), ingestion (D_{ing}), and dermal absorption through skin contact (D_{dermal}) will be calculated with the following formulas:

$$CDI_{inh} = C * \frac{R_{inh} * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{PEF * ABW * T_{avg}}$$

$$CDI_{ing} = C * \frac{R_{ing} * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{ABW * T_{avg}} * 10^{-6}$$

$$CDI_{dermal} = C * \frac{R_{dermal} * F_{exp} * T_{exp}}{ABW * T_{avg}} * 10^{-6}$$

Whereby C represents the elemental concentration (ppm), R_{inh} is the particulate matter inhalation rate in m³ day⁻¹, F_{exp} is the exposure frequency, T_{exp} is the time of exposure, PEF is the particle emission factor in m³ kg⁻¹, ABW is the average body weight (assumed 15 kg for children and 70 kg for adults), following US EPA [68], and T_{avg} is the average time for illness to develop (T_{exp} x 365 days).

SAF is the skin adherence factor in $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{hr}^{-1}$, A_{skin} is the exposed skin area in cm^2 , DAF is the dermal absorption factor as a ratio, and R_{ing} the particulate matter ingestion rate in mg day^{-1} . Details on these values can be found in Table 1. Afterwards, the Hazard Quotation (HQ) was calculated per element and ingestion.

$$HQ = \frac{CDI_{\text{inh,dermal,ing}} \cdot BAF}{RfD_0}$$

Whereby BAF is the bioaccumulation factor and RfD_0 is the reference dose, see Table 2. Finally, the Hazard Index (HI) is the sum of the HQ from the different intake paths, whereby an HI above 1 indicate that there are significant health risks, whereas a higher HI represents a higher possible impact. An HI value below 1 means that the particulate matter has a likely non-significant health effect.

Table 1. The values used to calculate the chemical daily intake (CDI)

Value	Adults	Child	Source
R_{inh} : Particulate matter inhalation rate	20 $\text{m}^3 \text{day}^{-1}$	7.6 $\text{m}^3 \text{day}^{-1}$	van den Berg 1994; Zheng et al. 2010
F_{exp} : Exposure frequency	180 day year ⁻¹	180 day year ⁻¹	Ferreira-Baptista and De Miguel 2005
T_{exp} : Time of exposure	24 years	6 years	USEPA 2001
PEF is the particle emission factor	$1.36 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$	$1.36 \cdot 10^9 \text{ m}^3 \text{kg}^{-1}$	USEPA 2001
ABW: average body weight	70 kg	15 kg	US EPA 1989
T_{avg} : average time of illness development	8,760 days	2,190 days	Zheng et al. 2010
SAF: skin adherence factor	0.7 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{hr}^{-1}$	0.07 $\text{mg cm}^{-2} \text{hr}^{-1}$	USEPA 2001
A_{skin} : exposed skin area	5700 cm^2	2800 cm^2	USEPA 2001
DAF: dermal absorption factor	0.001	0.001	USEPA 2001

Table 2. The reference dose values (RfD₀) used to calculate the hazard quotation (HQ) per element. The data has been provided by the US EPA [84] and Hu et al. [82].

Element	(RfD ₀)
As	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Cd	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Co	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Cr	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Cu	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Fe	$7.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Mn	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Ni	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Pb	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$

4. Enrichment factor

The chemical composition of the dust particles in parts per million (ppm) will be transformed into an enrichment factor (EF) normalized to the aluminium concentration. The formula for this calculation is:

$$EF = \frac{X_{\text{dust}}}{Al_{\text{dust}}} / \frac{X_{\text{UCC}}}{Al_{\text{UCC}}}$$

Where X_{dust} en X_{UCC} is the elemental concentration in ppm in the dust and the upper continental crust (UCC), respectively, and Al_{dust} and Al_{UCC} is the concentration of aluminium in the dust and UCC, respectively. Aluminium is chosen as the reference element due to its significance in clay minerals, correcting their presence. The UCC concentration data are sourced from Wedepohl [83], as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The concentration of elements in ppm in the upper continental crusts as presented by Wedepohl [83].

Al	Si	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
77440	303480	53	35	527	30890	11.6	18.6	14.3	52
As	Se	Sr	Mo	Cd	Sn	Sb	Ba	Hg	Pb
2	0.083	316	1.4	0.102	2.5	0.31	668	0.056	17

5. Meteorological data

To compare the relationship between $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentration and wind conditions, the wind velocity and wind direction measured at a climate station at Langebaanweg were used. This is hourly data that was provided by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) from the Integrated Surface Database (ISD).

